

Supplementary Information

to

Solution atomic layer deposition of smooth, continuous, crystalline metal-organic framework thin films

Maïssa K. S. Barr,^{1,*} Soheila Nadiri,¹ Dong-Hui Chen,² Peter G. Weidler,² Sebastian Bochmann,¹ Helmut Baumgart,^{3,4} Julien Bachmann,¹ Engelbert Redel^{2,*}

¹ *Department of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Friedrich-Alexander University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Chemistry of Thin Film Materials, IZNF, Cauerstr. 3, 91058 Erlangen, Germany*

² *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute of Functional Interfaces (IFG), Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany*

³ *Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Old Dominion University, Norfolk, Virginia 23529, USA*

⁴ *Applied Research Center at Jefferson Labs, Newport News, Virginia 23606, USA*

Description of the sALD setup. The deposition of Cu-BDC was carried out in a custom-built microfluidic reactor equipped with peristaltic original equipment manufacturer pumps as described earlier by Y. Wu¹, J. Fichtner² and V. Koch (Figure 1).³ The sALD controller and software were provided by ZUMOlabor. The peristaltic pumps (EOM, Watson-Marlow model 400A, 0–24 V), the Teflon tubes (OD 1.16 mm, ID 1.0 mm), the fluoroelastomer tubing (ID 1.52 mm) and the Luer-Lock fittings were purchased from Watson-Marlow. The microfluidic reactor is made from Teflon, where four inlets supply the precursors and solvent to the sALD reactor chamber. The first (pump A) and the fourth (pump B) inlets are dedicated to delivering

the two required precursors, while the second (pump S) inlets are dedicated to supplying the purge solvent. The Teflon chamber is closed with a microscope glass slide (soda lime glass from Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG) and a thick acrylic glass piece with holes for screws fixed on the metallic bottom holder. The glass slide was cleaned with detergent in distilled water, isopropanol and acetone and dried in N₂ flow. The quartz crystal microbalance ("openQCM" was purchased from Novaetech) is connected at the outlet of the chamber.

Figure S1. Quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) measurements of Cu-BDC showing a linear growth for an sALD pulse/ exposure/ purge sequence of 30 s / 30 s / 90 s

Figure S2. Schematic representation of the growth sequence of Cu-BDC by sALD highlighting the Cu-BDC unit cell.

Figure S3. (a) PM-IRRAS, and (b) Raman spectra of Cu-BDC grown by sALD with 50 and 200 ALD cycles

Figure S4. X-ray diffractogram of Cu-BDC grown by sALD after 200, 300, 400 cycles establishing crystal growth.

Figure S5. SEM micrograph of Cu-BDC films grown with 10, 30, 65 and 75 sALD cycles.

Figure S6. (a) SEM cross-section micrograph and (b) EDX spectrum from the top view of Cu-BDC films grown with 40 sALD cycles. The film appears to be a compact layer and the atomic ratio of the different elements confirms the presence of Cu-BDC.

Figure S7. AFM micrograph of Cu-BDC films grown with 65 sALD cycles (a) untreated area (b) area after the removal of tape.

1. Fichtner J., Wu Y., Hitzenberger J., Drewello T., Bachmann J. Molecular Layer Deposition from Dissolved Precursors. *ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology* 2017, **6**(9): N171-N175.
2. Koch V. M., Barr M. K. S., Büttner P., Mínguez-Bacho I., Döhler D., Winzer B., Reinhardt E., Segets D., Bachmann J. A solution-based ALD route towards $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)(\text{PbI}_3)$ perovskite via lead sulfide films. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 2019, **7**(43): 25112-25119.
3. Wu Y., Döhler D., Barr M., Oks E., Wolf M., Santinacci L., Bachmann J. Atomic Layer Deposition from Dissolved Precursors. *Nano Letters* 2015, **15**(10): 6379-6385.